

EXTENDED DATA

Title: Delirium and Cognitive Screening in National Hip Fracture Registries: Scoping Review Protocol

Author names:

Niamh A. Merriman¹

Rose S. Penfold²

Louise Brent³

Pamela Hickey⁴

Mary E. Walsh⁵

Eithne Sexton⁶

Tara Coughlan⁷

Alasdair M. J. MacLulich⁸

Antony Johansen⁹

Cristina Ojeda-Thies¹⁰

Andrew J. Hall¹¹

Catherine Blake¹²

Author affiliations and contact details:

¹School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; niamh.merriman1@ucd.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5327-7762>

²Edinburgh Delirium Research Group, Ageing and Health and Advanced Care Research Centre, Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, United Kingdom; rose.penfold@ed.ac.uk; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7023-7108>

³National Office of Clinical Audit, Dublin, Ireland; louisebrent@noca.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9129-235X>

⁴National Office of Clinical Audit, Dublin, Ireland; pamelahickey@noca.ie.

⁵School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland and School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Science, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland University of Medicine and Health Sciences, Dublin, Ireland; maryewalsh@rcsi.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8920-7419>

⁶School of Population Health, Royal College of Surgeons in Ireland University of Medicine and Health Sciences, Dublin, Ireland; eithnesexton@rcsi.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5564-7771>

⁷Discipline of Medical Gerontology, School of Medicine, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland and Department of Age-related Healthcare, Tallaght University Hospital, Dublin, Ireland; tara.coughlan@tuh.ie.

⁸Edinburgh Delirium Research Group, Ageing and Health, Usher Institute, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, United Kingdom; a.maclulich@ed.ac.uk; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3159-9370>

⁹School of Medicine, University Hospital of Wales, Cardiff and School of Medicine, Cardiff University, Cardiff, United Kingdom and National Hip Fracture Database (NHFD), Falls and Fragility Fracture Audit Programme, Royal College of Physicians, London, United Kingdom; antony.johansen@wales.nhs.uk; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4726-9106>

¹⁰Department of Surgery, School of Medicine, Complutense University of Madrid; Department of Traumatology and Orthopaedic Surgery, Hospital Universitario 12 de Octubre, Madrid, Spain; cristina.ojeda@salud.madrid.org; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7052-1491>

¹¹School of Medicine, University of St. Andrews, St. Andrews, United Kingdom; ajh52@st-andrews.ac.uk; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4582-8368>

¹²School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science, University College Dublin, Dublin 4, Ireland; c.blake@ucd.ie; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0600-629X>

Corresponding author:

Dr Niamh A. Merriman
School of Public Health, Physiotherapy and Sports Science,
University College Dublin,
Dublin 4,
Ireland
Email: niamh.merriman1@ucd.ie

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Full Search Strategy

Sources: MEDLINE (Ovid), Embase (Elsevier), CINAHL (EBSCO)

MEDLINE (Ovid)

Resources: Ovid MEDLINE(R) Epub Ahead of Print and Ovid MEDLINE(R) 1946 to current

	Medline Ovid
1	Hip Fractures/ OR hip fracture*.ab,ti.
2	((Hip fracture adj3 registry) OR (hip fracture adj3 registries) OR (National Hip Fracture Registry) OR (National Hip Fracture Register) OR (Hip fracture adj3 database) OR (Hip fracture adj3 audit*)).ab,ti.
3	((quality register).ab,ti. OR (quality registry).ab,ti. OR (performance indicator*).ab,ti. OR (quality indicator*).ab,ti.) AND (hip fracture).ab,ti.
4	((Audit adj2 guideline*) OR (registry adj2 guideline*)).ab,ti.
5	2 OR 3 OR 4
6	1 AND 5

Embase (Elsevier)

EMBASE on Elsevier.com	
1	'hip fracture\$':ti,ab OR 'hip fracture'/exp
2	'hip fracture' NEXT/3 registry OR 'hip fracture' NEXT/3 registries OR 'National Hip Fracture Registry':ti,ab OR 'National Hip Fracture Register':ti,ab OR 'hip fracture' NEXT/3 audit\$
3	(('quality register':ti,ab OR 'quality registry':ti,ab OR 'performance indicator*':ti,ab OR 'quality indicator*':ti,ab) AND 'hip fracture':ti,ab,de,kw)
4	(Audit NEXT/2 guideline\$) OR (registry NEXT/2 guideline\$)
5	2 OR 3 OR 4
6	1 AND 5
7	#6 AND [humans]/lim AND [english]/lim
8	#7 AND [medline]/lim
9	#7 NOT #8

CINAHL (EBSCO)

	CINAHL
1	(MH "Hip Fractures+") OR TI 'hip fracture\$' OR AB 'hip fracture\$'
2	('hip fracture' N3 registry) OR ('hip fracture'N3 registries) OR TX 'National Hip Fracture Registry' OR TX 'National Hip Fracture Register' OR ('hip fracture' N3 audit\$)
3	(TX 'quality register' OR TX 'quality registry' OR TX 'performance indicator\$' OR TX 'quality indicator\$') AND (TI 'hip fracture\$' OR AB 'hip fracture\$')
4	(Audit N2 guideline\$) OR (registry N2 guideline\$)
5	S2 or S3 or S4
6	S1 and S5
7	Limit to English

Data extraction template for items relating to delirium and cognition currently collected by national hip fracture registries.

Hip Fracture Registry General Details	Registry name (country)	
	Age of inclusion (years)	
	Year started	
	Year of latest published report	
	No registered in last annual report	
	No of participating hospitals	
	Types of cases included	
	Phase of care included	
	Level of coverage	
	Delirium standards of care	
	Cognition standards of care	
	Follow up (days)	
	Participation (Mandatory or Voluntary)	
	Funding	
Delirium Assessment	Delirium included	
	Question/Specific Tool	
	Response options	
	Eligible patient population	
	Timing of assessment	
	Frequency of assessment	
	HCP responsible	
	No patients screened Time 1	
	No patients who screened positive Time 1	
	No patients screened Time 2	
	No patients who screened positive Time 2	
	No patients screened Time 3	
No patients who screened positive Time 3		
Cognitive Assessment	Cognition included	
	Question/Specific Tool	
	Response options	
	Eligible patient population	
	Timing of assessment	
	Frequency of assessment	
	HCP responsible	
	No patients screened Time 1	
	No patients who screened positive Time 1	
	No patients screened Time 2	
	No patients who screened positive Time 2	
	No patients screened Time 3	
No patients who screened positive Time 3		

HCP – healthcare professional; No – number.